

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

Volume I Issue V

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

SEPTEMBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

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ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

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NORMAN S. ANDALES, MPM

Instructor III / BSTM OJT Coordinator

Biliran Province State University

Naval, Biliran Province, Region VIII, Philippines

[DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17069474](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17069474)

Guardians of the Islands: A Call for Sustainable Tourism

In islands pure, where cultures gleam,
The Philippines welcomes every dream.
Tourism's pulse, the economy's heart,
Draws millions here, a vibrant art.

Yet voices rise with urgent plea,
For tourism, in a kind and sustainably.
Not just the earth we seek to guard,
But lives and culture are rich and hard.

From Palawan's enchanted shore,
To terraces that legends bore,
Our treasures vast, a precious hold,
Yet threatened now, their stories told.

Over-tourism's heavy hand,
Destruction scars this fragile land.
Boracay, once a haven bright,
Closed its doors to heal its plight.

Six months of care, the island sought,
Waste and growth problems were fought.
Though costs were felt in short-term pain,
Preserving beauty was the gain.

Sustain the earth, empower the folk,
Keep wealth within, and spread the hope.
Tourism fuels both jobs and pride,
But only when all are allied.

Support local hands, respect old ways,
Let culture thrive through all our days.
Siargao's balance shows the way,
Where growth and nature can both stay.

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Awareness grows in every heart,
Tourists, locals play their part.
Choose eco-stays, protect the wild,
Walk softly, like a mindful child.

Governments lead with plans and laws,
But shared responsibility draws
Communities, businesses, and guests,
To protect what we love best.

Sustainable tourism lights the way,
For futures bright as a new day
Where profits meet the earth's embrace,
And culture finds its rightful place.

The Philippines' true wealth, its voice,
Lies in its people, our shared choice.
Together, hand in hand we stand,
Guardians of this precious land.